

Adding Every Arabic Periodical Published Before 1930 to Wikidata

Moving the Scholarly Crowdsourcing Project Jarā'id to the Digital Commons

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Abstract

This paper documents the contribution of comprehensive bibliographic data on all Arabic periodicals published before 1930 to Wikidata, the largest public and open knowledge graph. The dataset originated with the scholarly crowdsourcing project Jarā'id and comprises information on more than 3,000 periodicals, about 2,700 editors and almost 350 holding institutions. As a living union list of Arabic periodicals, the dataset alleviates the infrastructural weaknesses of library catalogues and discovery systems, as well as the epistemic violence of knowledge ecologies. The move to Wikidata addresses the socio-technical shortcomings of our original approach by making the dataset available in a FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) and five-star Linked Open Data environment. In addition, the platform provides multilingual interfaces and robust user management and version control, which significantly improves the usability and maintenance of evolving datasets. The paper details workflows and data models and demonstrates the reusability of our approach in other contexts with a second dataset of periodicals from the Ottoman Empire. Finally, the paper shows how the move to Wikidata generates continuous engagement with wider Wikimedia communities that significantly broaden our knowledge about periodicals and their holdings.

Keywords: Linked Open Data, Wikidata, periodical studies, Arabic periodicals, bibliographic data

إضافة جميع الصحف العربية الصادرة قبل سنة ١٩٣٠م إلى ويكي بيانات
انتقال مشروع المصادر الجماعية الأكاديمية
"جرائد" إلى المشاع الرقمي

يوثق هذا البحث مساهمة البيانات الجغرافية الشاملة لجميع الدوريات العربية المنشورة حتى عام ١٩٣٠ في ويكي بيانات (Wikidata)، أكبر رسم بياني معرفي حر ومفتوح. نشأت مجموعة البيانات من مشروع "جرائد" لتعميد المعلومات الشاملة الجماعي عن تاريخ الصحافة العربية وتتضمن معلومات عن أكثر من ٣٠٠٠ دورية، وحوالي ٢٧٠٠ محرر، وما يقرب من ٣٥٠ مكتبة وأرشيف ومجموعات أخرى. باعتبارها قائمة اتحادية حية للدوريات العربية، تعالج مجموعة البيانات نقاط الضعف الهيكلية لفهارس المكتبة، وأنظمة الاكتشاف بالإضافة إلى العنف المعرفي للنظم البيئية للمعرفة. تتناول الخطوة نحو ويكي بيانات أوجه القصور الاجتماعية والتقنية في نهجنا الأصلي عن طريق جعل مجموعة البيانات متاحة بشكل عادل وفي بيئة بيانات مفتوحة مرتبطة بخمسة نجوم. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، توفر المنصة واجهات متعددة اللغات وإدارة مستخدمين قوية وتحكم الإصدارات مما يحسن بشكل كبير قابلية الاستخدام وصيانة مجموعات البيانات المتطورة. يفصل البحث سير العمل ونماذج البيانات ويظهر إمكانية إعادة استخدام نهجنا في سياقات أخرى باستخدام مجموعة بيانات ثانية للدوريات من الدولة العثمانية ونشرت باللغة التركية العثمانية. وأخيراً يوضح البحث كيف أن الانتقال إلى ويكي بيانات يؤدي إلى مشاركة مستمرة مع مجتمعات الويكي الأوسع والتي توسع بشكل كبير معرفتنا بالدوريات ومقتنياتها في مكتبات

Keywords in Arabic: البيانات مفتوحة مرتبطة، ويكي بيانات، دراسات الدوريات، الصحافة العربية، بيانات بليوجرافية

Data availability statement

Data and code are available under free and open licences:

1. Snapshot of the Arabic periodicals dataset from Wikidata: Grallert (2024a).
2. XSLT for mapping TEI/XML to custom XML of the Wikidata data model: Grallert (2024b).
3. JSON schemas for the upload from OpenRefine to Wikidata: Grallert (2025c).
4. SPARQLqueries: Grallert (2025d).

Introduction

Imagine there was a discovery system that allowed a historian to query for all sources written or published in a specific geographic region around a particular period, identifying those that still survive in libraries or archives—or even better, those that have been digitised and are available online. Wouldn't that be wonderful? As a social historian interested in collective action in the Eastern Mediterranean, I would not have to dig through finding aids, media histories or union catalogues to establish a list of contemporary newspapers that might have reported on a series of food riots across the cities and towns of what is now Palestine, Lebanon, Syria and Israel during the summer of 1910, only to then discover through lengthy communications with colleagues and knowledge-preservation institutions around the globe that no copies could be found of what ought to be there.

This is not just a dream. In the following, I argue that all the components for such a discovery system are readily available and free to use for everyone with the means to access the internet. Against the backdrop of two datasets of bibliographic metadata on almost 4,000 Arabic and Ottoman periodicals, including more than 2,700 editors and almost 350 holding institutions, this article documents the motivation, workflows and data models for contributing such information to [Wikidata](#) as the core of such a discovery system.

The problem

Scholars and prospective readers of periodicals depend on the interfaces of discovery systems for finding and locating materials of interest. Contrary to common perceptions of networked information systems, it is surprisingly difficult to locate copies of periodicals (cf. Gaskelle 2017). This is due to a combination of factors. Firstly, such systems frequently do not allow for browsing based on the criteria outlined above. Instead, they focus on keyword search as an entry point into collections (cf. LeBlanc 2024; Zaagsma 2023; Sherratt 2019; Milligan 2019). Secondly, aggregators such as [OCLC's WorldCat](#) or the [German Zeitschriften Datenbank \(German Union Catalogue of Serials, ZDB\)](#) gather and present cataloguing data of varying quality and depth as they are provided by libraries and other holding institutions at regional, national and transnational levels. Thirdly, catalogues in turn should be considered living artefacts of socio-technical infrastructures with myriads of historical layers of knowledge production and organisation. They depend on the knowledge and skills of their cataloguers and are limited by ever-changing technical affordances, resulting in all sorts of hacks and (what we would now consider) errors. Comprehensive bibliographies or union lists and catalogues of all published works in a given language or genre can fill the gaps between what is found in catalogues and what was published and therefore might have survived in some collection.

But they are prohibitively expensive to produce and maintain, even for a finite number of publications.

This lack of (available) knowledge is particularly relevant for the first mass media of Arabic-speaking communities around the globe. Early Arabic magazines and journals, such as Butrus al-Bustani's *الجنان* (*al-Jinān*, Beirut, 1876–1886), Ya'qub Sarruf, Faris Nimr and Shahin Makariyus's *المقتطف* (*al-Muqtaṭaf*, Beirut and Cairo, 1876–1952), Muhammad Kurd 'Ali's *المقتبس* (*al-Muqtabas*, Cairo and Damascus, 1906–1918/1919) or Rashid Rida's *المنار* (*al-Manār*, Cairo, 1898–1941) were formative forums for a transnational Arabic public sphere, emanating and debating everything from modern science and Islamic reform to foreign literature, the Arabic (cultural) renaissance (*nahḍa*), socialism or the role of women, and coining a new Arabic terminology in the process. Being able to go beyond the small number of well-known titles from Cairo and Beirut will allow us to actually engage with them as an ideosphere spanning communities between Jakarta, Baghdad, Khartoum and Rio de Janeiro, while each of the thousands of Arabic newspapers could be invaluable sources for local microhistories.

In the following, I introduce our dataset of Arabic periodicals and discuss the strengths and weaknesses of our original approach, which, although based on minimal computing, relied on custom implementations that made it hard to maintain and did not reach users beyond a small academic community (section 2). I then discuss [Wikidata](#) as a platform that addresses the socio-technical shortcomings of our original approach by making the dataset available in a FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) and five-star Linked Open Data environment with multilingual interfaces, robust user management and version control, and a vibrant community of contributors (section 3). Section 4 details data models, tools and workflows for contributing bibliographic data to Wikidata. The results section (section 5) situates the contribution in the larger context of periodical data on Wikidata and introduces practical use cases for research projects and GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives and museums) institutions for the dataset based on the results of various SPARQL queries. I also demonstrate the general reusability of the data models and workflows with a second dataset of some 700 Ottoman periodicals. The final discussion (section 6) focuses on the experiences within the first year of the initial contribution to Wikidata and how the dataset evolved through the efforts of other Wikidata users and bots.

Project Jarā'id

[Jarā'id: A Chronology of Arabic Periodicals \(1800–1929\)](#) is an ongoing scholarly crowdsourcing effort to address the shortcomings of supposedly comprehensive (printed) histories (e.g. Tarrazi 1913–1914, 1933; an electronic text was only

published recently: Tarrazi 2023; Ayalon 1995) by compiling a digital, and thus searchable, union list of all Arabic periodicals published before 1930. It was initiated by Adam Mestyan in the early 2010s and I have been involved in the project as one of its main contributors and lead on data modelling and first iterations of the website since 2012. Starting from a modest table of a few hundred titles in a Microsoft Word document, Jarā'id has grown into a catalogue with more than 3,200 entries, recording bibliographic data and, more importantly, holding information in original scripts and Latin transcription (titles, editors, publishers, places of publication, date of first issue and publication languages). Dozens of scholars have contributed information based on their own research in libraries and private collections worldwide. As well as being the only comprehensive union list of such material, Jarā'id is the only one that can be searched and browsed in the original script.

Datasets

There are currently two versions of the Project Jarā'id dataset.

1. The original dataset was published in tabular form as TEI/XML (TEI Consortium 2020) on [GitHub](#) and [Zenodo](#). We additionally generated multiple iterations of static websites from this dataset, which served as the main interface for users (Mestyan, Grallert, et al. 2020; Mestyan and Grallert 2012–2015, 2020).
2. I significantly expanded the original dataset and data model in semantically richer formats based on TEI `<biblStruct>` nodes. This enriched dataset is based on my research in periodicals, archives and, more recently, library catalogues and digital facsimile collections, such as [HathiTrust](#), the [ZDB](#) and Lebanese libraries like the American University of Beirut (AUB), Université Saint-Esprit de Kaslik (USEK) and Université Saint-Joseph (USJ) in Beirut, based on public APIs (Application Programming Interfaces), web scraping and personal collaborations with library staff (see Grallert 2022).¹

It is the latter dataset I published to Wikidata and will discuss below.

Data model

Periodicals are somewhat difficult to model as they are socio-technical assemblages: in other words, groups of people using various technologies and tools to publish (meaning to compose, print and distribute) a collection of texts from various genres under a shared title and with a fixed frequency. What ends up in collections are material artefacts—individual copies of specific periodical issues. As material artefacts, these are easy to record and model. But as scholars

1. I especially thank Elie Kahale (AUB) for his support.

interested in periodicals as a historical phenomenon and a source documenting historical events, we are concerned with the larger assemblage, whose parts, including publication titles and places can, and frequently do, change over time (cf. Gaskelle 2017).

Identifying and delineating the assemblage poses some challenges. Sometimes, continued publication—the fundamental periodicity of periodicals—was more of an aspirational claim than a reality. The medical journal الطيب (*al-Ṭabīb*), for instance, was originally published as أخبار طبية (*Akḥbār Ṭibbiyya*) in Beirut by George Post, and edited by John Wortabet and William van Dyck, in January 1874. In May that year, they changed the title to الطيب (*al-Ṭabīb*). Publication ceased in 1876. The journal was revived in 1881 with Shahin Makariyus, a well-known journalist and prolific editor, as a manager. Publication was stopped in 1882 due to controversies over Darwin’s theory of evolution, and Makariyus left Beirut for Cairo.² الطيب (*al-Ṭabīb*) resumed publication with a new volume count in March 1884 and came to yet another halt in 1885. The journal reappeared after a 10-year hiatus until its final demise with the outbreak of World War I (Sa’di and Sarton 1938).³ There are good arguments for cataloguing this journal as either a single periodical, five individual titles or a combination thereof. Holding libraries of the full publication run, such as AUB and USJ, chose the former, while others took the volume count starting in 1884 as a clue to the journal’s start date.

In contemporaneous sources, periodicals were identified by their titles and, if necessary, places of publication. The same is true for the ruling authorities, with whom publishers had to apply or register their planned endeavours in most jurisdictions.⁴ We therefore assume, as do most catalogues, that different titles signify different publications and grant each its own entry in our union list.⁵ We link successive titles through pointers. This decision also caters to those who search for a specific title without in-depth knowledge of individual publication histories.

A closely related challenge is how to model publishers moving to new places, and sometimes continents, and taking their periodical operations with them. Technically, they will have had to acquire a new permit, licence or concession. We should thus model such “moving” publications as new titles and successors of their publishers’ previous periodical, particularly if volume and issue counts

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2. On this episode, known as the “Lewis Affair,” see Farag (1972).
 3. Surviving artefacts show that Tarrazi provided an evidently incorrect account of the title’s publication history (2023, 289–92).
 4. For the legal history of periodical publishing in the Ottoman Empire, see Boyar (2006, 20–22) and Grallert (2014, 45–49, 62–63). Cioeta (1979) and Ayalon (1995) ignore legal developments and paint a rather static picture.
 5. Cf. Gaskelle (2017). Tildesley (2009) points to the endemic nature of title changes in the nineteenth-century press of Great Britain and Ireland.

did not continue. Library catalogues and union lists follow this practice save for a number of very famous and influential journals, such as *المقتطف* (*al-Muqtataf*), which moved operations from Beirut to Cairo in 1884; the journal *المقتبس* (*al-Muqtabas*), moving from Cairo to Damascus after the Young Turk Revolution of 1908; the newspaper *الهدى* (*al-Hudā*), moving from Philadelphia to New York in 1903; and the newspaper *الأهرام* (*al-Ahrām*), moving from Alexandria to Cairo in 1898.

Why such a dataset?

I have covered the reasons and necessity for creating such datasets elsewhere in some detail (Grallert 2021, 2025a, 2025b). They can be summarised as historical layers of technical affordances deeply rooted in Western, colonial perceptions of the Other, whose main result is a common lack of support for non-Latin scripts across the entire technology stack and, consequently, the absence or inaccessibility of datasets in languages that rely on such writing systems (cf. Fiormonte et al. 2015). Comprehensive information on the publication history of the Arabic press was generally inexistent and information on titles surviving in library collections was practically inaccessible in any systematic form prior to Project Jarā'id.

In the following, I will only provide a pertinent example to illustrate the state of affairs: Between 1919 and 1938, Bulus Shahade published the weekly newspaper *مرآة الشرق* (*Mir'āt al-Sharq*) in Jerusalem. As can be seen from the linked Wikidata item, this newspaper is available in a significant number of libraries in Palestine, Israel, Lebanon, the US and Germany. At least two of these provide digital facsimiles. But how would one know? Or, rather, how would one find the title in catalogues?

Figure 1: Masthead of *Mir'āt al-Sharq* no. 1, 17 September 1919

Source: National Library of Israel.

Mir'āt al-Sharq is, of course, a Latinisation of the Arabic original *مرآة الشرق*. It follows the widely adopted system of the (American) *International Journal of Middle East Studies* (IJMES) (IJMES, n.d.; Library of Congress 2012). The same is true for rendering the name of its editor, *بولس شحادة*, as *Bulus Shahade* (note that IJMES does not employ diacritics for personal names). Cataloguers in German-speaking countries would employ a different system with 1:1 character transliterations aiming at phonetic replication, originally devised by the *Deutsche Morgenländische Gesellschaft* (DMG) (Brockelmann et al. 1935; DIN 2011; ISO 1984). They Latinise the title as *Mir'āt aš-Šarq*. French scholarly practices are subtly different and record the paper as *Mir'āt al-Šarq*. Note that the Arabic original, as well as the diacritics utilised in the transcriptions, require support for Unicode character encodings for display and search/retrieval operations. Other, historical, technical transcription systems designed pure ASCII representations such as “mir'_a=t a l-^sarq” to address this problem.⁶ The newspaper itself, published in Palestine during the British Mandate, provided the transliteration *Meraat al-Shark* in its masthead (fig. 1).

Discovery systems and catalogue frontends frequently either do not support Arabic script or the underlying catalogue data does not provide information in the original script. In addition, the Latinisation is prone to error. Cataloguers either make mistakes or the machines at their command do not support the appropriate diacritics, resulting in an even larger variety of possible (mis)spellings. Consequently, records have not been merged in aggregating catalogues. Finally, search algorithms commonly deploy some sort of fuzzy matching that mostly removes diacritics—or simply any non-ASCII characters, retaining only the 26 letters of the English alphabet. They might also support wildcards, such as “*” to stand in for any character.

To find holdings of *مرآة الشرق* (*Mir'āt al-Sharq*) one will, therefore, have to search for “Mir'āt al-Sharq” or “Mirat Sharq” in English catalogues such as the [British Library](#) or OCLC's [WorldCat](#), which has at least eight different records for this title. The former also holds Arabic cataloguing data for this title, but cataloguers wrongly recorded *مرآة الشرق* instead of *مرآة الشرق*. German and French catalogues, like the [ZDB](#), the [Catalogue collectif de France \(CCFR\)](#) or the [Bibliothèque nationale de France \(BnF\)](#) do not support the internationally more common *Mir'āt al-Sharq*, but will return hits for “Mir'āt aš-Šarq”, “Mir'at as-sarq”, or even “Mirat Sarq” and “Mir*a* sarq”. Note that the historical phonetic French transcription would have used “ch” instead of “š” for *ش*. The BnF has also catalogued some of their holdings in Arabic and supports search in the original script (this is not the case for the CCFR aggregating the BnF data).⁷

6. Wittern (2013); Unicode Consortium (2022). On the background of Unicode and its application to Arabic, see Nemeth (2017, 400–406); Milo (1999); cf. Romanov ([2015] 2021).

7. The resulting hit in the BnF catalogue leads to another periodical of the same title.

Strength: Overview of uncoordinated digitisation efforts

One of the strengths of Project Jarā'id's dataset is the way it enables a first systematic look into the surviving traces of collection-building efforts and the state of digitisation over the last decades. Table 1 shows the percentage of titles with known holdings and digital remediations. At the time of writing, we can only locate 775 (21.83%) of all 3,550 titles in the dataset in collections. Of these, almost one third, 233 (6.56% of all titles), have digital remediations. The percentage for digitised titles in collections is surprisingly high, but we cannot resolve information on the extent of such digitisation, which varies between a single issue and an entire course of publication. More importantly, the dataset also provides an astonishing insight into the uncoordinated nature of scanning efforts: 66 periodicals or 28.33 percent of all digitised periodicals have been digitised by multiple institutions and 21 of this subset by three and more. Considering the limited resources and relatively high cost of digitisation, it would surely make sense if future efforts were directed towards those titles not yet digitised at all. Making this information readily available and queryable through Wikidata contributes to this goal.

Table 1: Periodical holdings and digitised copies

Periodicals	up to 1918		up to 1929	
Published	2,054		3,550	
Known holdings	540		775	
% of total		26.29		21.83
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Digitised	156		233	
% of known holdings		28.89		30.06
% of total		7.59		6.56
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Multiple digitisations	51		66	
% of total		2.48		1.86
% of digitised		32.69		28.33

Weaknesses

Jarā'id has a number of weaknesses for users, contributors and maintainers, almost all of them rooted in its nature as an unfunded, volunteer-driven research project.

Users looking for information on Arabic periodicals

Almost all users of Jarā'id as a union list will access the data through the [project website](#), which is implemented as a static site and is currently hosted on GitHub. Updates to the source TEI/XML will trigger an automatic regeneration of the website.

1. The website has only limited visibility beyond those already in-the-know. Somebody searching for Arabic periodicals will either consult established discovery systems such as library catalogues or aggregating platforms, or conduct a web search, where the website will not be prominently ranked.
2. The website has only limited usability. Data is presented in tabular form with a number of indexes. Some core fields have been automatically re-transcribed into the original Arabic script, while more concise information is provided in Latinised transcription and English notes. The surrounding interface is written solely in English. Search is implemented through the browser's full-text search function. Browsing is limited to a number of indexes for publication places and editors, but they provide only Latinised transcriptions.

Both points severely limit the circle of potential users to a small community of academic researchers.

Contributors

Contributions can be submitted either via email to the project maintainers or, for the more technically savvy, by directly editing the source and opening a pull-request on GitHub. While this ensures that project editors can vet contributions, it also introduces technical barriers and depends on editors maintaining the project ad infinitum.

Maintainers

The current setup follows minimal computing principles in an attempt to balance “what do *we* need?” with “what do *we* have?” (Gil and Ortega 2016; Risam and Gil 2022, emphasis mine) It has very few overheads and can be easily downloaded, archived and moved to other servers. However, it depends on a number of commercial services (notably GitHub) and requires maintainers to not just curate the dataset but to design and maintain a website and workflows for updating the site's content.

Wikidata

Wikidata is the largest public knowledge graph with hundreds of millions of items, published under CC0 licence.⁸ Such a graph organises structured

8. See <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Statistics> for up-to-date statistics.

information about items in statements that construct relations between items, such as “*Mir’āt al-Sharq* is a newspaper,” “*Mir’āt al-Sharq* was first published on 17 September 1919,” “*Mir’āt al-Sharq* was published in Jerusalem,” “Jerusalem is a city,” “*Mir’āt al-Sharq* was founded by Bulus Shahade,” “Bulus Shahade was a human being,” etc. Such statements are expressed as properties and should be attributed to a source (another item or URI). Statements can carry further qualifiers, such as temporal information or indications of the certainty of a claim. Even though Wikidata (in)famously does not adhere to a strict ontology and is frequently referred to as a “folksonomy” (see Manzo et al. 2015) characterised by communities of modelling practices, only very few of which are documented, it does have data models. All properties have data types and might come with a set of rules that will result in warnings if violated—although there is no strict technical enforcement of these rules and they are, consequently, frequently violated (or, at least, ignored).⁹ The only exception to this rule seems to be items lacking labels, descriptions and the [instance of \(P31\)](#) property. Without the latter, which identifies the fundamental nature of an item as being, for instance, a [newspaper \(Q11032\)](#), items are left detached from the larger knowledge graph. If no other item links to them, some housekeeping bots might eventually delete them.

In addition to being a huge source of data—and arguably more importantly—Wikidata is an international community of active volunteers. It is also a project of the Wikimedia Foundation and a sister project to Wikipedia. The software it runs on, [Wikibase](#), is maintained as free and open-source software (FOSS) (Vrandečić, Pintscher, and Krötzsch 2023).

Wikidata addresses all the weaknesses of Project Jarā'id, as outlined above: Firstly, Wikidata inherently adheres to the FAIR principles by making all data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable on practicable levels (GO FAIR 2020). Our current setup provided interoperable and reusable data, but was severely lacking in findability and accessibility. Wikidata, on the other hand, is highly visible to search engines and aggregating platforms and provides a multilingual interface supporting all languages within the limits of Unicode. People looking for Arabic periodicals will actually be able to find them with our data published in Wikidata. These advantages are matched on the technical side, where Wikidata provides five-star Linked Open Data (Berners-Lee 2009), in other words, machine-readable structured data in non-proprietary formats, adhering to open standards, with a public domain licence (CC0), and linking to other people’s data through multiple APIs, including SPARQL endpoints. Linking

9. OpenRefine claims that [ALA-LC romanization \(P8991\)](#) is not designed for use as a qualifier, even though that is exactly how it appears in all examples. The Wikidata frontend itself does not reject this use of P8991, e.g. <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q124963763>.

to Wikidata is enabled by canonical identifiers for all items and properties and by permanent URIs for each edit.¹⁰

Secondly, Wikidata is a well-established open infrastructure with large communities of users, contributors and maintainers, which far exceeds anything we as scholars could ever achieve on our own on an infrastructural level. As such, it is increasingly adopted as a platform to share authority data by GLAM institutions and research projects (Fagerving 2023; Allison-Cassin and Scott 2018; Odell, Lemus-Rojas, and Brys 2022; Sardo and Bianchini 2022; Zhao 2023). Thirdly, Wikidata, like its sister projects Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons, is a community-driven platform and provides easy tools for collaboratively editing and contributing data. The threshold for joining Project Jarā'id's crowd-sourcing effort on Wikidata is thus in practice lowered to having access to a device with an internet connection.

Finally, maintaining a dataset of thousands of periodicals, people and organisations is extremely challenging and prone to errors when data is kept in a collection of tables and XML files. Wikidata, on the other hand, provides a plethora of tools for data cleaning, deduplication and reconciliation that significantly ease maintenance work.

Weaknesses

Wikidata, of course, has weaknesses of its own. Scholars and GLAM institutions are commonly wary of ceding control over “their” datasets to volunteer-driven, radically open projects. While vandalism does not constitute a significant problem, misidentification of items and erroneous edits occur on a daily basis. The larger problem, however, is bulk uploads of datasets from research projects and GLAM institutions creating large numbers of duplicates, which require detection and merging.¹¹

Quality and distribution of data

Unsurprisingly, data quality and consistency vary widely across Wikidata, and biases in coverage mirror those of the digital realm writ large: Latin script, European/colonial languages, predominantly English, the Global North. For

10. In fact, Wikidata recommends always referencing the versioned permanent URL instead of the canonical ID; see <https://www.wikidata.org/w/index.php?title=Special:CiteThisPage&page=Q25212027&id=2313077072&wpFormIdentifier=titleform> for citations of <https://www.wikidata.org/w/index.php?title=Q25212027&oldid=2313077072>.

11. Private communications with Wikimedia Deutschland in 2024. See Sahu-Hough (2025) for similar arguments and observations.

example, before contributing our datasets in mid-March 2024,¹² Wikidata contained information on almost 30,000¹³ periodicals published before 1930 (fig. 2), but only 93 of them were Arabic periodicals (fig. 3).

Figure 2: Map of all periodicals (items created before 18 March 2024), SPARQL query

Figure 3: Map of all Arabic periodicals (items created before 18 March 2024), SPARQL query

Almost 11,000 or roughly one third of the total carried no language information at all (the titles and labels of them were almost exclusively written in Latin script). The remaining dataset was surprisingly tilted towards Swedish—a rather minor language on the global scale, but apparently one with a strong Wikidata

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12. Wikidata does not provide the date of an item's creation through APIs. I therefore used the sequentially assigned IDs of items as an indirect marker and used the ID of an item with a known creation date as a filter, assuming that all items with lower IDs would have been created before (see Gray 2019).
 13. Wikimedia provides persistent, short URLs for SPARQL queries and their results, but the link shortener has a fixed length for input URLs of 2,000 characters. This limit is easily breached with queries containing non-ASCII symbols that will need expensive URL encoding (Wikimedia Foundation 2025). I therefore use <https://query-chest.toolforge.org/>, a similar service specifically designed for SPARQL queries.

Related projects

Other projects have contributed (smaller) datasets on periodicals to Wikidata before, for example [Agents of Change: Women Editors and Socio-Cultural Transformation in Europe, 1710–1920 \(WeChangEd\)](#) (Thornton et al. 2022) and the National Library of Wales (NLW). The latter spearheaded the usage of Wikidata as a union catalogue for periodicals. Wikidata Visiting Scholar Simon Cobb and National Wikimedian Jason Evans, both at the National Library of Wales, added hundreds of Welsh periodicals to Wikidata from 2017 onwards and linked them to holding institutions.¹⁵ However, their example had not generally caught on and only about 1,200 of the almost 30,000 Wikidata items representing periodicals in mid-March 2024 linked to holdings in specific collections ([SPARQL query](#)).

Data model

The most important aspect of contributing data to an existing dataset is mapping our local data model (TEI/XML `<biblStruct>`s, see appendix A) to the target model of Wikidata items and properties (fig. 5). All modelling decisions serve a specific purpose (cf. Stachowiak 1973). In our case, I wanted to maximise the discoverability of periodicals and holdings while maintaining as much of the semantic expressiveness of our original data model as possible. Given the nature of Wikidata's folksonomy outlined above, data models on the platform largely exist as shared social practices, which are then enacted by SPARQL queries. I therefore looked at existing periodicals and WikiProjects to develop a basic data model of Wikidata properties for our dataset (Wikimedia Foundation 2022).

```

1  PREFIX medium: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1002697>      # set a publication type:
                                                                    periodicals (wd:Q1002697),
                                                                    newspapers (wd:Q11032)
2  SELECT DISTINCT
3    ?periodical ?dateOnset
4  WHERE {
5    VALUES ?dateOfInterest                                     # set a date of interest
6    {"1930-01-01"^^xsd:dateTime}.
7    ?periodical wdt:P31/                                       # limit to medium
8    wdt:P279* medium: ;
9    (wdt:P571 |
10   wdt:P580) ?dateOnset.
11   ?periodical wdt:P407/                                       # limit by publication language
12   wdt:P279* wd:Q13955.                                       (Arabic = Q13955)
13   FILTER(?dateOnset <                                       # published before a specific
14   ?dateOfInterest).                                         date
15 }
16 ORDER BY ?dateOnset
17 LIMIT 4000

```

15. This is evidenced by contributions from their accounts, [Sic19](#) and [Jason.nlw](#).

Figure 5: Schematic drawing of our data model for periodicals

Most statements have been removed for illustrative purposes.

To avoid creating duplicates, I had to reconcile our dataset with existing Wikidata items. I could not, therefore, directly generate [QuickStatements](#), a simple text format for directly manipulating Wikidata items, but had to import our data into [OpenRefine](#) first. OpenRefine is a well-established tool for data wrangling and reconciliation of various data sources, initially released in 2010. It also supports parsing of XML. However, directly importing `<tei:biblStruct>` proved unfeasible as this would have required a direct 1:1 mapping between the TEI and Wikidata or extensive data manipulation in OpenRefine with [GREL](#) (General Refine Expression Language), a language I am not overly familiar with. In addition, mixed-content nodes containing both plain text and child elements are a common feature in TEI/XML. They also proved nigh impossible to resolve with OpenRefine. I therefore implemented a mapping to the Wikidata data model as custom XML through transforming our TEI/XML source with [XSLT](#) stylesheets. For easier human readability, this custom XML uses Wikidata’s property IDs as element names (e.g. `<wd:P407>` for `<tei:textLang>` expressing the publication language of a periodical) and employs XML’s native tree structure to map qualifiers and references (see appendix B).

The intermediate step of using OpenRefine for reconciliation then necessitates the actual mapping from OpenRefine fields to Wikidata. This is done through OpenRefine’s interface. The resulting JSON schemas have been exported for sharing and reuse (Grallert 2025c).

Mapping scripts and languages

Mapping language and script information proved difficult. HTML5 and TEI/XML use BCP 47 language tags (Network Working Group 2009) in their language attributes, which allow users to freely combine tags for language and script, such as “ar-Latn-x-ijmes” for formally describing “Arabic, written in Latin script using a private transliteration scheme called IJMES.” Yet, Wikidata

does not strictly separate information on language and script. It provides its own language tags for monolingual text fields, which can only be edited by the development team (Wikimedia Foundation 2024).

Creativity was thus required. One option is to provide the original Arabic title and add transliterations through a qualifier. This would explicitly demonstrate that the transcription was not found on the material artefact. However, there is currently only a single property for one of the myriad Latin transcriptions of Arabic or Ottoman Turkish beyond the generic [transliteration or transcription \(P2440\)](#)¹⁶: namely, [ALA-LC romanization \(P8991\)](#), which for all practical purposes is similar to the IJMES transcription (Library of Congress 2012). Proposing new properties, which might require lengthy discussions with the community of Wikidata editors and might stall for years, seemed insufficiently promising in the short term. Yet, I consider such proposals a worthwhile endeavour for the most common transcriptions of languages written in Arabic script and I plan to submit them in the future. However, using qualifiers leaves three issues. First, our original dataset does not explicitly link transcriptions to original script, leaving a small number of “dangling” transcriptions which cannot be unambiguously associated with an original. Second, such usage of qualifiers is currently not very common. A [SPARQL query](#) for publications (not restricted to periodicals) with transliterated titles using P2440 returns 184 items. The overwhelming majority of these works are written in Uzbek.¹⁷ Using such a rarely deployed property as P2440, while feasible, would therefore not necessarily increase the findability of our data. Third, qualifiers cannot be further qualified, which means that we cannot provide individual sources for transliterations.

On the other hand, there are numerous examples of wrongly labelled languages on existing items for periodicals, where transcriptions carry the tag of either the target or source language. This is particularly true for Hebrew periodicals, for example “Hadashot” as the English title of [חדשות \(Q1058638\)](#) or “Mekiyлта” as the Hebrew title of [מכילתא \(Q120618180\)](#). The aforementioned WECHANGED project equally recorded some Latinised transcriptions of Greek titles, such as “Estiades” for [Εστιάδες \(Q88564665\)](#), as Greek titles. I followed this example and (wrongly) labelled transcriptions of Arabic, Ottoman and Ladino with their target language in other words “English,” “German” and “Turkish” respectively. I also followed this approach for transcriptions provided in the mastheads of periodicals themselves (see fig. 1). This was done with a view to the discoverability and retrievability of data points through simpler SPARQL queries without qualifiers. However, the current iteration of the XSLT stylesheets for converting TEI/XML to the custom XML of our Wikidata data model also supports mapping transcriptions to the relevant qualifiers and we will amend existing items accordingly.

16. I thank one of the anonymous reviewers for bringing this property to my attention.

17. There are also a small number of items which employ P2440 for translations of the title.

Workflow

The Jarā'id dataset connects four types of entities: periodicals, people (as editors, founders and publishers), organisations (holding institutions) and places. For the time being, I excluded historical organisations such as publishers and printing shops, as we have not systematically recorded them in our input data. Each type of entity requires a multistep upload process:

1. **Reconcile** all properties whose data type is a Wikidata item with existing items in order to avoid creating duplicates. Depending on the data model, this can quickly result in hours and hours of semi-automatic work. The step is significantly helped by persistent identifiers (PIDs) from other authority files, such as [OCLC](#) for publications, [VIAF](#) for people, or [GeoNames](#) for places, which we have already integrated in our dataset as far as possible. Note also that OpenRefine utilises the reconciliation service API, which is not language-agnostic (World Wide Web Consortium 2023). It is important to ensure the language of the API matches the language of the data.¹⁸
2. **Create** new Wikidata items for all unreconciled entities. This was done in batches directly from within OpenRefine.
3. **Integrate** identifiers of newly created and reconciled Wikidata items (QIDs) into our local dataset in order to maintain the link between the two. This was done through processing data exports (CSV) from OpenRefine and merging the QIDs into the TEI/XML with XSLT.
4. **Link** and enrich Wikidata items. As items for different types of entities, such as periodicals and editors, were created independently from each other, the newly created items then had to be cross-linked through OpenRefine; for example, *مرآة الشرق* (*Mir'āt al-Sharq*) and its editor بولس شحادة (Bulus Shahade) were linked through [P112](#) and [P108](#).

Finally, we also decided to **archive** all Wikidata items relevant to our project. Easy and practically unrestricted access to editing items is one of Wikidata's greatest strengths, but also its main weakness from the point of view of the academic community. Data will change, and although one can reference a specific version of a Wikidata item with a PID, Wikidata is not a repository for long-term data preservation and might cease operating. Thus, we wrote the necessary scripts to periodically download, version and push subgraphs to code-sharing platforms and research-data repositories (Dresselhaus and Grallert 2024; Grallert 2024a).

Results

During the initial phase, I added high-quality bibliographic information for more than 3,000 Arabic periodicals, including 2,728 editors and 347 holding

18. I thank one of the anonymous reviewers for pointing me to the API documentation to address this subtlety.

institutions, increasing the total from 93 to 3,248 titles as of 8 August 2024 (fig. 6). Most of these entities required creating new Wikidata items and linking them together.

Figure 6: Map of all Arabic periodicals (items created up to 8 August 2024), SPARQL query

Answering research questions

Having added our dataset to Wikidata allows for the sort of complex queries imagined in the introduction to this article—queries which are otherwise impossible to execute in common discovery systems or in the published tabular form of Jarā'id. Using Wikidata's SPARQL endpoint, we can answer our initial research questions and display the results on an interactive map: Which local newspapers existed at the time of the food riots of summer 1910 in the Eastern Mediterranean (fig. 7)? Where can I find surviving holdings (fig. 8)? Or, even better: Which periodicals can be instantaneously accessed as digitised copies (fig. 9)?

Figure 8: Map of newspapers published in the Eastern Mediterranean during the summer of 1910 with known holdings, SPARQL query

Figure 9: Map of newspapers published in the Eastern Mediterranean during the summer of 1910 with digitised copies, [SPARQL query](#)

One can also use Wikidata to answer questions regarding the visual language and potential regional preferences for specific front page layouts. The relevant [SPARQL query](#) linking places of publication with digital facsimiles of periodicals does not yet yield enough results for a meaningful analysis (fig. 10), but it demonstrates the potential of such visual approaches for browsing and quick classification (broadsheet, multi-column, illustrated). One could rather easily write a bot that follows the links to openly accessible facsimiles provided through our efforts. It could then use machine vision to identify front pages, download a copy and add the image file to WikiCommons if the digitised items are in the public domain. Finally, it would then link these images to the Wikidata items for the relevant periodicals with [P18](#).

Figure 10: Section of the graph connecting places of publication with images of Arabic periodicals published before 1930, SPARQL query

Guiding future digitisation efforts

GLAM institutions stand to benefit immensely from the cross-linking of records between Wikidata and aggregating platforms, authority files and library catalogues. This not only increases the visibility of their collections to wider audiences, but also backlinks to Wikidata based on queries for identifiers from WorldCat (OCLC), the Library of Congress (LoC) or the Zeitschriften Datenbank (ZDB) already available in their cataloguing data, and would make it possible to pull in additional information such as titles in original scripts and complementary collections. Summary statistics on collections (table 2) or digitised periodical titles (table 3) can help direct the limited funds for costly digitisation efforts towards titles that are not yet scanned or those in urgent need of preservation. This would prevent all too common uncoordinated and redundant digitisation efforts.

Table 2: Result of the SPARQL query ranking periodicals by the number of collections they are found in

rank	periodical	periodicalLabel	countCollections
1	Q124972743	al-Mashriq	50
2	Q15856582	Al-Hilal (magazine)	40
3	Q6033538	Al-Muqtataf	31
4	Q286468	Al-Ahram	30
	Q124964344	Majallat al-Majmaʿ al-ʿilmī	30
5	Q65563187	Al-Jinan	24
6	Q4118576	Al-Musawar	16
7	Q6793025	Rose al-Yūsuf	14
	Q17521078	Ad-Diya	14
	Q4702794	Al-Manar	14
	Q12207336	Hadiqat al-Akhbar	14
8	Q124970439	Majallat al-Ustādh	13
9	Q22018602	Az-Zuhur	12
10	Q21605653	Al-Bayan (journal)	11
	Q108084719	Al Bashir	11
	Q124970913	al-Jawāʿib	11
11	Q6559136	Lisan al-Hal	10
	Q43032686	al-Siyāsa al-Usbūʿiyya	10
12	Q124972736	al-Masarra	9
	Q127427564	al-Jāmiʿa al-ʿUthmāniyya	9
	Q124973866	Rawḍat al-Madāris al-Miṣriyya	9

Table 3: Result of the SPARQL query ranking periodicals by the number of times they were digitised

rank	periodical	periodicalLabel	countDigitised
1	Q22018602	Az-Zuhur	13
2	Q15856582	Al-Hilal (magazine)	11
	Q124970439	Majallat al-Ustādh	11
3	Q4702794	Al-Manar	9
	Q12237314	Lughat Al Arab	9
	Q6033538	Al-Muqtataf	9
4	Q19259751	At-Tabib	8
	Q21605653	Al-Bayan (journal)	8
5	Q12238943	Al-Irfan	7
	Q17521078	Ad-Diya	7
6	Q124974308	Majallat al-Azhar	6
	Q65563187	Al-Jinan	6
	Q124972743	al-Mashriq	6

rank	periodical	periodicalLabel	countDigitised
7	Q4118576	Al-Musawar	5
	Q124972674	al-Marʿa al-Jadida	5
	Q124973866	Rawḍat al-Madāris al-Miṣriyya	5
8	Q124972207	al-Funūn	4
	Q127427564	al-Jāmiʿa al- ʿUthmāniyya	4
	Q124970827	al-Jāmiʿa	4

Reuse of data models and workflows

Once data models and mappings are set up, they can be easily reused for additional datasets. To test this claim, I added hundreds of periodicals from Baykal’s wonderful index for the press of the Ottoman Empire between 1908 and 1914 (Baykal 2019) to Wikidata. The index is based on documentation found in the Ottoman state archives, contemporary accounts (Hakki Bey 1909) and the Hakki Tarık Us Collection (HTU) at Beyazıt State Library. Although the book was only digitally published in unstructured form, the open-access PDF is of sufficient quality to automatically extract the relevant information.¹⁹ I then transformed the extracted data into our familiar `<tei:biblStruct>`s with a combination of regular expressions and XSLT stylesheets. This yielded structured bibliographic information on more than 1,800 periodical titles in all languages of the Ottoman Empire: Ottoman Turkish, Arabic, Armenian, Greek Persian, and so on.

Unfortunately, the index is difficult, if not impossible, to reconcile with existing datasets due to the transcription practices for non-Latin scripts outlined above. Ottoman Turkish was written in Arabic script until the script reform of 1928, when Turkey adopted the Latin alphabet (cf. Fortna 2023; Kirmizialtin and Wrisley 2022). Baykal follows the established practice of Ottomanists and provides modern Turkish renditions for all titles and personal names originally written in non-Latin scripts, such as Arabic, Greek, Judeo-Arabic (in Hebrew script), Karamanlıca (Turkish in Greek script), Ladino (Spanish in Hebrew script) or Ottoman Turkish in Armenian or Hebrew scripts. To my knowledge there exist no readily available tools for an automated reconversion into the original scripts.

As a consequence, I have only uploaded information on 706 Ottoman Turkish periodical titles from Baykal’s index to Wikidata. The existing number of items was small enough to manually reconcile with our dataset. It included mostly

19. I used [pdfx](#).

multilingual periodicals added through our initial contribution of the Jarā'id dataset (SPARQL queries for Ottoman periodicals [before](#) and [after our upload](#)).

Regarding data quality, it must also be noted that Baykal provides only very limited information on publication places. The reason is not entirely clear. Large sections of the Hakkı Tarık Us Collection were digitised and published more than 15 years ago (Baykal 2011; Kirmizialtin and Wrisley 2022). Even though the DjVu format for images was already outdated at the time, it can still be accessed with readily available browser plug-ins,²⁰ making it possible to establish publication places for all of the 500-odd titles in HTU that are listed in the index without locations (out of a total of 722 periodicals). Unfortunately, it seems Baykal only consulted the catalogue.²¹

Discussion

The overall experience of contributing data to Wikidata in bulk is positive. Tools and processes are sufficiently documented and members of the community are rather helpful. Tweaking data models and figuring out some quirks in OpenRefine for macOS (always start from the Java applet launcher!) turned out to be the most time-consuming step. Once the latter was established, it became apparent that Wikimedia maintains a rather aggressive blocklist of IP ranges to prevent people using VPNs to access the site from editing, even when they are logged in and thus identifiable to the system. This particularly impacts contributors living under authoritarian regimes—be they located in the Eastern Mediterranean or North America—who rely on VPNs to escape the surveillance of their governments or the oligarchical corporations running the backbones of our linked knowledge ecologies.

The Wikidata community

People and bots began to contribute data and perform maintenance and data cleaning operations within hours of my initial uploads. Look, for instance, at the journal of *الجملة* (*al-Majalla*), published in Buenos Aires from 1915 onwards. I created the item on 18 March 2024 and automatically added information over the course of the next month. One month later, the user “[Sempta](#)” amended information on Spanish-language titles, location of headquarters, and even added a facsimile of the front page. Based on the facsimile, I was then able

20. Such as [DjVu.js Viewer for Firefox](#).

21. A cursory search for three random titles within this sample confirmed that locations and directors of publication (*mudīr al-mas'ūl*, literally “the responsible director”) were indeed provided in mastheads as stipulated by law.

to add subtitles and a publication interval.²² Some human users contribute Latinised transcriptions of Arabic names, such as “Mahmud Ali” for محمود علي,²³ while bots and one diligent user managed to find duplicates and merged them. Thus, for instance, some rudimentary items had been created by bots based on Wikipedia entries for Arabic periodicals in the early 2010s. But these items contained nothing beyond the title of the Wikipedia page and a link to it. In the absence of any statement identifying them as Arabic periodicals, I did not find these items and would have had no capacity to check the linked Wikipedia page, to see whether they should indeed represent a periodical.²⁴

In a small number of cases, human users were too eager to find duplicates and merged clearly distinct items. This has, so far, mostly happened to items for periodical editors and commonly occurred when users did not follow due diligence by ignoring available statements, such as conflicting life dates or locations. To prevent repeated attempts to merge the same items, I have added the statement *different from* (P1889) pointing to the item not to be merged.²⁵ While the number of such misattributions remains small, one still might want to periodically check merges.

Discovery of new titles

Querying Wikidata also returned titles that ought to have been included in the Project Jarā'id dataset but were not covered by the sources we consulted or found in archives and libraries visited by our contributors. Take, for example, *אלחוררייא* (*al-Hurriyya*), a Judeo-Arabic newspaper published in Tangier between 1915 and 1922. Even though none of the information provided on Wikidata is properly referenced, the item points to the catalogue of the National Library of Israel and links to a digital facsimile of the newspaper's front page, which confirm most of the statements.

Conclusion

In this paper, I propose a radically open and democratic approach to some of the scholarly primitives as formulated by John Unsworth—“basic functions common to scholarly activity across disciplines, over time, and independent of theoretical orientation” (Unsworth 2000)—namely, discovering and referring. I present arguments as to why we, as communities of scholars, should gather

22. See the [history of edits for Q124972416](#).

23. See the [history of edits for Q125160798](#).

24. [Original state of the item for Birjīs Bārīs before it was merged with our data](#).

25. For example <https://www.wikidata.org/w/index.php?title=Q12249620&oldid=2336434318> and <https://www.wikidata.org/w/index.php?title=Q125160089&oldid=2336434650>.

and share our collective knowledge of ephemeral cultural artefacts through Wikidata and the socio-technical infrastructure underpinning this particular project within the wider Wikiverse. The paper then thoroughly documents how we can contribute substantial datasets to Wikidata in practice.

I develop my argument against the backdrop of our long-running Project Jarā'id to crowdsource publication histories of all Arabic periodicals published globally before 1930 and document their surviving copies. As a validated union list, the dataset is of immense value to researchers, librarians and the wider public. It remedies many of the fundamental shortcomings of compartmentalised library catalogues and aggregating platforms with their built-in epistemic violence of habitually monolingual—indeed English—technology stacks. However, a dataset is practically irrelevant if it cannot be readily found, accessed and ultimately integrated into the specific workflows and needs of its potential users. In this regard, Project Jarā'id, like so many other scholar-led and underfunded initiatives, should be considered a failure, even though we provide data in a well-established and documented exchange format.

Integrating our datasets into Wikidata solves almost all of the infrastructural problems: Wikibase, the software powering Wikidata and its sister projects, is a well-maintained and open solution, providing well-documented interfaces for human users and machines, as well as the necessary user management for collaborative editing. All user interfaces cater to the linguistic diversity of humanity through support for almost all living languages and scripts (as far as they can be encoded in Unicode). The well-established and thriving community of Wikidata contributors and users, including automated bots for data cleaning and enriching based on external identifiers, will connect us to new communities with interest in and knowledge about the materials we care deeply about. Data on Wikidata might not be as semantically rich as our TEI-based data model, but it is FAIR data with clear licences and fulfils all criteria for five-star Linked Open Data as soon as we link to external catalogues and holdings. Wikimedia Foundation, the organisation behind Wikidata, will outlive anything we can set up within the project-based logic of academic funding. Wikidata, however, is a living project and not a long-term archive despite thorough versioning with stable URIs.

Ultimately, the workflows, data models and code to transform and map bibliographic data from TEI/XML to Linked Open Data, to integrate it into Wikidata and to archive parts of the knowledge graph in public repositories are meant as an invitation. Our experiences with adopting the approach for another dataset demonstrate that other scholars and communities can do likewise with relatively little effort.

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Appendices

Appendix A – TEI/XML

Exemplary TEI/XML <biblStruct> for the newspaper *Mir'āt al-Sharq* demonstrating our data model. Note how mixing Latin and Arabic script on a single line causes display issues and how Arabic is erroneously rendered from left to right (e.g. lines 4–8).

```
<biblStruct source="https://projectjaraaid.github.io oape:org:73
oape:org:420 wiki:Q124857769" subtype="newspaper" type="periodical">
  <monogr source="oape:org:420">
    <title level="j" xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</title>
    <!-- removed source information (@source) -->
    <title level="j" type="alt" xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</title>
    <title level="j" type="sub" xml:lang="ar">جريدة اسبوعية حرة</title>
    <title level="j" type="sub" xml:lang="ar">جريدة عربية سياسية حرة</title>
    <title level="j" xml:lang="ar-Latn-EN">Meraat al-Sherk</title>
```

```

<title level="j" xml:lang="ar-Latn-x-ijmes">Mir'āt al-Sharq</title>
<title level="j"xml:lang="ar-Latn-x-dmg">Mir'āt aš-Šarq</title>
<title level="j"type="alt" xml:lang="ar-Latn-FR">Meraat alsherq</
title>
<title level="j"type="sub" xml:lang="ar-Latn-x-dmg">ġarīda usbū'īya
hurra</title>
<title level="j"type="alt">Meraat Al-Sherk</title>
<title level="j"type="alt">Meraat al-Shark</title>
<idno type="AUBNO">Mic-NA:000350</idno>
<idno type="OCLC">33001662</idno>
<idno type="jaraid">t1r2801</idno>
<idno type="oape">3513</idno>
<idno type="wiki">Q25212027</idno>
<idno type="zdb">1019615-8</idno>
<!-- removed more identifiers -->
<textLang mainLang="ar"/>
<editor type="owner">
<persName ref="jaraid:pers:2325 oape:pers:1405 wiki:Q125160760"
xml:lang="ar-Latn-x-ijmes">Būlus Shaḥāda</persName>
<persName ref="jaraid:pers:2325 oape:pers:1405 wiki:Q125160760"
xml:lang="ar"><forename>بولس</forename> <surname>شهادة</surname></per-
sName> </editor>
<editor type="editor">
<persName ref="oape:pers:2636 wiki:Q125159749" xml:lang="ar">
<forename>نقولا</forename> <surname>شهادة</surname> </persName> </editor>
<imprint>
<pubPlace>
<placeName ref="geon:281184 oape:place:6 wiki:Q1218"
xml:lang="und-Latn">Jerusalem</placeName>
<placeName
ref="geon:281184 oape:place:6 wiki:Q1218" xml:lang="ar">القدس</
placeName> </pubPlace>
<publisher> <orgName xml:lang="ar">مطبعة مرآة الشرق</orgName> </
publisher>
<date type="onset" when="1919-09-17">1919</date>
<date source="oape:org:73" type="terminus" when="1938">1919-1938</
date>
<!-- removed more dates -->
</imprint>
</monogr>
<note type="holdings"> <list>
<item source="https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/2413018-7">
<label><orgName ref="isil:DE-1w oape:org:287" type="short">Ber-
lin SBB Zeitungsabteilung</orgName> </label>
<listBibl>
<bibl> <idno subtype="DE-1w" type="classmark"
>Ztg 10664 MR</idno> <date type="onset" when="1919">1919</
date> <date type="terminus" when="1938">1938</date> </bibl>
</listBibl> </item>
<item source="oape:org:73">

```

```

    <label> <placeName ref="geon:276781 jaraid:place:2 oape:place:26
wiki:Q3820" resp="#xslt"
    >Beirut</placeName>, <orgName ref="jaraid:org:hAUB oape:org:73"
xml:lang="en">AUB</orgName> </label>
    <ab xml:lang="ar"
    >30 (في المكتبة:مج:1.ع:1- س-مج:20.ع. 1347) 1919: ايلول-17 آذار</ab>
    <listBibl>
    <bibl> <idno subtype="AUB" type="classmark">Mic-NA:000350</
idno> </bibl>
    </listBibl> </item>
    <item source="https://projectjaraid.github.io">
    <label> <placeName ref="geon:281184 oape:place:6 wiki:Q1218"
resp="#xslt">Jerusalem</placeName>, <orgName ref="jaraid:org:hEAP119
oape:org:63" xml:lang="und-Latn">Aqṣā</orgName> </label>
    <listBibl>
    <bibl>1922-1936 ()<idno subtype="self" type="URI">https://eap.
bl.uk/collection/EAP119-1-24</idno><idno type="classmark">EAP119/1/24</
idno>, </bibl>
    </listBibl> </item>
    </list> </note>
</biblStruct>

```

Appendix B – Custom XML for Wikidata mapping

The same data for the newspaper *Mir'āt al-Sharq* as transformed into a custom XML with XSLT stylesheets. It uses Wikidata's property IDs as element names. Note how mixing Latin and Arabic script on a single line causes display issues and how Arabic is erroneously rendered from left to right (e.g. lines 5–6).

```

<item xml:id="Q25212027">
  <label xml:lang="en">Mir'āt al-Sharq</label>
  <description xml:lang="en">newspaper published in Jerusalem between
1919 and 1938</description>
  <label xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</label>
  <description xml:lang="ar">جريدة تصدر في القدس بين سنة 1919 و 1938</description>
  <P31>
    <P854>https://projectjaraid.github.io</P854>
    <P854>https://www.aub.edu.lb/libraries/Pages/default.aspx</P854>
    <P854>https://zdb-katalog.de/</P854>
    <P248>Q124857769</P248>
    <QItem>Q11032</QItem>
  </P31>
  <!-- removed source information (P854, P248) -->
  <P31>
    <QItem>Q1002697</QItem>
  </P31>
  <!-- titles -->
  <P1476>
    <string xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</string>
  <P8991>

```

```

    <string>mir'āt al-sharq</string>
  </P8991>
</P1476>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="ar">مرأة الشرق</string>
  <P8991>
    <string>mir'āt al-sharq</string>
  </P8991>
</P1476>
<P1680>
  <string xml:lang="ar">جريدة اسبوعية حرة</string>
</P1680>
<P1680>
  <string xml:lang="ar">جريدة عربية سياسية حرة</string>
</P1680>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="en">Meraat al-Sherk</string>
</P1476>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="en">Mir'āt al-Sharq</string>
</P1476>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="de">Mir'āt aš-Šarq</string>
</P1476>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="fr">Meraat alsherq</string>
</P1476>
<P1680>
  <string xml:lang="de">ğarīda usbū'īya ħurra</string>
</P1680>
<P1476>
  <string>Meraat Al-Sherk</string>
</P1476>
<P1476>
  <string>Meraat al-Shark</string>
</P1476>
<P243>
  <string>33001662</string>
</P243>
<QItem>Q25212027</QItem>
<P1042>
  <string>1019615-8</string>
</P1042>
<!-- removed more identifiers -->
<P407>
  <QItem>Q13955</QItem>
</P407>
<!-- editors -->
<P112>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>

```

```

</P112>
<P127>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>
</P127>
<P98>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>
</P98>
<P98>
  <QItem>Q125159749</QItem>
</P98>
<P2561 xml:lang="ar">
  <string xml:lang="ar">حنا سمعان</string>
</P2561>
<!-- imprint -->
<P291>
  <string>Jerusalem</string>
  <QItem>Q1218</QItem>
</P291>
<P571>
  <date>1919-09-17</date>
</P571>
<P580>
  <date>1919-09-17</date>
</P580>
<P582>
  <date>1938</date>
</P582>
<!-- removed more dates -->
<!-- holding information -->
<P195>
  <P854>https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/2413018-7</P854>
  <string>Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin - Preußischer Kulturbesitz,
Zeitungssammlung</string>
  <QItem>Q28777973</QItem>
  <P580>
    <date>1919</date>
  </P580>
  <P582>
    <date>1938</date>
  </P582>
  <P217>
    <string>Ztg 10664 MR</string>
  </P217>
</P195>
<P195>
  <P854>https://www.aub.edu.lb/libraries/Pages/default.aspx</P854>
  <string>The Library of the American University in Beirut</string>
  <QItem>Q124855340</QItem>
  <P217>
    <string>Mic-NA:000350</string>

```

```

    </P217>
  </P195>
  <P195>
    <P854>https://projectjaraid.github.io</P854>
    <string>al-Aqṣā Mosque Library</string>
    <QItem>Q22684743</QItem>
    <P217>
      <string>EAP119/1/24</string>
    </P217>
    <P953>
      <string>https://eap.bl.uk/collection/EAP119-1-24</string>
    </P953>
  </P195>
</item>
<item xml:id="Q25212027">
  <label xml:lang="en">Mir'āt al-Sharq</label>
  <description xml:lang="en">newspaper published in Jerusalem between
1919 and 1938</description>
  <label xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</label>
  <description xml:lang="ar">جريدة تصدر في القدس بين سنة 1919 و 1938</description>
  <P31>
    <P854>https://projectjaraid.github.io</P854>
    <P248>Q186844</P248>
    <P248>Q124855340</P248>
    <P248>Q107011742</P248>
    <QItem>Q11032</QItem>
  </P31>
  <!-- removed source information (P854, P248) -->
  <P31>
    <QItem>Q1002697</QItem>
  </P31>
  <!-- titles -->
  <P1476>
    <string xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</string>
    <P2440>
      <string xml:lang="en">Meraat al-Sherk</string>
    </P2440>
    <P8991>
      <P854>https://projectjaraid.github.io</P854>
      <P248>Q186844</P248>
      <P248>Q124855340</P248>
      <P248>Q107011742</P248>
      <string xml:lang="en">Mir'āt al-Sharq</string>
    </P8991>
    <P2440>
      <P248>Q186844</P248>
      <string xml:lang="de">Mir'āt aš-Šarq</string>
    </P2440>
  </P1476>
  <P1476>

```

```

<string xml:lang="ar">مرأة الشرق</string>
<P8991>
  <string>mir'āt al-sharq</string>
</P8991>
</P1476>
<P1680>
  <P248>Q186844</P248>
  <string xml:lang="ar">جريدة اسبوعية حرة</string>
  <P2440>
    <P248>Q186844</P248>
    <string xml:lang="de">ğarīda usbū'īya ħurra</string>
  </P2440>
</P1680>
<P1680>
  <P248>Q124855340</P248>
  <string xml:lang="ar">جريدة عربية سياسية حرة</string>
</P1680>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="fr">Meraat alsherq</string>
</P1476>
<!-- identifiers -->
<P243>
  <string>33001662</string>
</P243>
<QItem>Q25212027</QItem>
<P1042>
  <string>1019615-8</string>
</P1042>
<!-- removed more identifiers -->
<P407>
  <QItem>Q13955</QItem>
</P407>
<!-- editors -->
<P112>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>
</P112>
<P127>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>
</P127>
<P98>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>
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  <QItem>Q125159749</QItem>
</P98>
<P2561 xml:lang="ar">
  <string xml:lang="ar">حنا سمعان</string>
</P2561>
<!-- imprint -->
<P291>

```

```

    <string>Jerusalem</string>
    <QItem>Q1218</QItem>
</P291>
<P571>
    <date>1919-09-17</date>
</P571>
<P580>
    <date>1919-09-17</date>
</P580>
<P582>
    <date>1938</date>
</P582>
<!-- removed more dates -->
<!-- holding information -->
<P195>
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    <string>Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin - Preußischer Kulturbesitz,
Zeitungssammlung</string>
    <QItem>Q28777973</QItem>
    <P580>
        <date>1919</date>
    </P580>
    <P582>
        <date>1938</date>
    </P582>
    <P217>
        <string>Ztg 10664 MR</string>
    </P217>
</P195>
<P195>
    <P854>https://www.aub.edu.lb/libraries/Pages/default.aspx</P854>
    <string>The Library of the American University in Beirut</string>
    <QItem>Q124855340</QItem>
    <P217>
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    </P217>
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    <QItem>Q22684743</QItem>
    <P217>
        <string>EAP119/1/24</string>
    </P217>
    <P953>
        <string>https://eap.bl.uk/collection/EAP119-1-24</string>
    </P953>
</P195>
</item>

```